

TRADITIONAL PHYTOTHERAPY OF PARASNATH HILLS, DISTRICT GIRIDIH (JHARKHAND), INDIA

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The Parasnath hills shows highest peak in Chotanagpur highlands and also remarkable diversity in its floristic elements. An effort has been made to give an account of Angiospermic plants in there, of which potential value among the tribal population observed. The present paper deals with ethno-medicinal uses of 101 species belonging to 84 genera and 54 families recorded from knowledgeable persons of the area.

Keywords- Parasnath hill, Tribal, Medico-Ethnobotany.

INTRODUCTION

Mount Parasnath and its adjacent area lies in the mid-eastern part of Chotanagpur highland which forms the easternmost extension of the Stable Indian Peninsular Block. Located between 86°03' E to 86°14' E longitudes and 23°55' N to 24°01' N latitudes, it forms the southern parts of Giridih district. Its elevation varies from less than 400m to over 1300m.

Survey of literature of earlier works of the area (Anderson, 1863; Kirtikar and Basu, 1935; Jain, 1963-90; Jain and Tarafder, 1963; Tarafder and Choudhari, 1981; Ambasta, 1986, Anonymous, 1986, Jain, Sinha and Saklani, 1989; Chopra, 1998) etc. have been ethnobotanically explored but the present study area has yet to be studied in detail. Keeping this in view the present study is undertaken to explore the ethno-medicinal wealth of the area.

The forests are mainly of monsoon sub-humid or tropical moist deciduous type. It is more luxuriant than the vegetation of adjoining Ganga plain in the north, because the higher elevations of the study area. Vegetation growing in these forests play a vital role in the economy and health of tribals.

METHODOLOGY

Extensive survey was conducted in more than 15 remote villages in Parasnath hill and adjoining areas from January 2003 to January 2005. To collect the information's, some proper knowledgeable informants, elderly people, headman of the hamlets, tribal medicine man, Baidya Rajs', 'Ojhas' and 'Mahrajs' were contacted, because they are the only source to collect the information's about local plant name and their uses. Ethnomedicinally important plants were collected and herbarium prepared. Plants were identified using local flora.

ENUMERATION

Abutilon indicum G. Don. (Malvaceae, Atibala)*RVY 13058

Leaves as tonic, its mucilage as lotion in rheumatism, roots infusion in fevers.

Acacia catechu Willd. (Mimosaceae, Khair or Katha) RVY 13013

Bark astringent given internally in acidity of the stomach and good antiseptic.

Acacia sinuata (Lour.) Merrill (Mimosaceae, Banritha) RVY 13090

Pods as detergent, powdered pods for hairwash to remove insects, emetic and expectorant.

Alangium salvifolium L.f. (Alangiaceae, Akarkanta) RVY 13105

Root bark anthelmintic and purgative, used in fevers, skin diseases, leaves as poultice in rheumatic.

Albizia odoratissima (L.f.) Benth. (Mimosaceae, Kala siris, Karmaru) RVY 13102

Bark in leprosy and inveterate ulcers, leaves with ghee in cough.

Albizia procera Benth. (Mimosaceae, Safed siris, Leaves insecticide and made into poultice to ripen boils.

Antidesma bunius Spreng. (Euphorbiaceae, Amati, Naikuti) RVY 13147

Leaves antidote to snake poison, extract in syphilis, bark poisonous.

Baliospermum montanum (Willd.) Muell.- Arg. (Euphorbiaceae, Dantiamoot) RVY 13146

Seed oil useful in rheumatism for external application, roots useful in jaundice, dropsy, leaf extract in asthma.

Bauhinia malabarica Roxb. (Caesalpinaceae, Karmai or Amli or Imli) RVY 13030

Young's flowers in dysentery.

Berberis asiatica Roxb. (Berberidaceae, Rasaut) RVY 13047

Root bark gives famous rasaut, menorrhagia, diarrhoea, jaundice and in skin diseases, powerful antiseptic, bark powder in fever.

Bombax ceiba L.(Bombacaceae, Semul or Simal) RVY 13092

Roots stimulant, tonic, a good medicine in sexual impotency, gum demulcent, haemostatic, used in diarrhoea, dysentery, menorrhagia, fruits in snake bite.

Butea monosperma (Lamk.) Taub. (Fabaceae, Palas or Dhak) RVY 13010

Gum in diarrhoea, leaves as tonic, bark in snake bite, flowers yield yellow dye antiseptic.

Callicarpa arborea Roxb. (Verbenaceae, Bagodi) RVY 13072.

Bark aromatic, bitter tonic and carminative, its decoction in skin troubles.

Capparis zeylanica L.(Capparidaceae, Ardanda) RVY 13059

Bark sedative, stomachic, given in cholera, leaves in swellings and boils.

Careya arborea Roxb. (Lecythidaceae, Kumbhi) RVY 13033

Bark in fever, in pox, flower and bark with honey as demulcent in coughs and colds, inner bark leech repellent, gum antiseptic.

Cassine glauca (Rottb.) O. Ktze (Celastraceae, Morindu) RVY 13069

Leaf powder as fumigatory to women for hysteria, as snuff to relieve headache, root bark water paste applied to swellings.

Celastrus paniculata Willd. (Celastraceae, Kanguni or Kujri) RVY 13067

Seeds stimulant, useful in rheumatism, leprosy, fevers and paralysis.

Centratherum anthelminticum (L.) Kuntze (Compositae, Somraj) RVY 13032

Powerful anthelmintic properties to remove hookworms and thread worms from stomach, seeds in skin troubles, tonic, diuretic.

Cissus adnata Roxb. (Vitaceae, Nadena) RVY 13051

Tubers blood purifier, powdered roots antiseptic, applied on wounds, cuts and fractures.

Cissus repanda Vahl (Vitaceae, Pureni) RVY 13106

Plant juice antiseptic, applied on bad smelling ulcers, boils.

Cleome monophylla L. (Capparidaceae, Hurhura) RVY 13055

Leaves externally applied to wounds ulcers, leaf juice in ear ache, seeds water paste applied externally in chronic painful joints.

Colebrookia oppositifolia Smith (Labiatae, Binda) RVY 13007

Roots in epilepsy, leaves paste in water applied in wounds and cuts, antiseptic.

Combretum roxburghii Spreng. (Combretaceae, Punk) RVY 13169

Leaves in the treatment of hematuric malaria.

Corchorus olitorius L. (Tiliaceae, Koshta) RVY 13163

Leaves demulcent, tonic, diuretic, useful in chronic cystitis, gonorrhoea, fibre widely used for Making antiseptic surgical dressings.

Cordia dichotoma Forst. (Boraginaceae, Bhairala) RVY 13148

Fruits given in troublesome urinary passage, lung and spleen troubles, antiseptic, bark decoction in fevers and dyspepsia, kernels in ringworm injection.

Croton roxburghii Balak. (Euphorbiaceae, Chucka) RVY 13066

Curculigo orchidoides Gaertn. (Amaryllidaceae, Kalimusli) RVY 13177

Rhizomes in piles, jaundice, asthma, diarrhoea, gonorrhoea, demulcent tonic, used as poultice in itch and skin irritation.

Dalbergia latifolia Roxb. (Fabaceae, Lalshisham) RVY 13128

Plant bitter tonic, stomachic, used in dyspepsia, diarrhoea, leprosy, obesity.

Dalbergia sissoo Roxb. (Fabaceae, Sissu or Shisham) RVY 13091

Leaf decoction in gonorrhoea, root and wood used in leprosy, boils, eruption of the skin.

Dalbergia volubilis Roxb. (Fabaceae, Bhatia) RVY 13074

Leaf juice as gargle in sore throat, applied to aphthae, root juice in gonorrhoea.

Dendrocalamus strictus (Roxb.) Nees. (Gramineae, Karail) RVY 13016 White calcium deposits on nodes, used tonic, given calcium deficiency. *Dendrophthoefalcata* (L.f.) Etlin (Loranthaceae, Banda) RVY 13025

Bark astringent, narcotic, useful in menstrual disorders, asthma, mania, antiseptic.

Desmodium gangeticum (L.) DC. (Fabaceae, Sarivan) RVY 13001

Roots astringent, tonic, diuretic used in fevers, dysentery, cough, vomiting.

Desmodium heterocarpon (L.) DC. (Fabaceae, Baephol) RVY 13144 Plant extract as tonic, given in coughs.

Desmodium oojeinensis (Roxb.) Ohashi (Fabaceae, Sandan) RVY 13048 Bark febrifugic and as fish poison, bark gum in diarrhoea.

Desmodium pulchellum Benth. (Fabaceae, Lodrom) RVY 13003 Bark extract in haemorrhages, diarrhoea, in food poisoning.

Desmodium velutinum (Willd.) DC. (Fabaceae, Chimbatti) RVY 13076

Root with peppers is given as enema in blood urination.

Dillenia indica L. (Dilleniaceae, Chalita or Chalta) RVY 13008

Calyx of fruits in digestion, tonic, leaves astringent, fruit juice as cooling beverage, in fevers and cough mixture.

Dioscorea bulbifera L. (Dioscoriaceae, Ratauloo) RVY 13035

Dried rhizomes antiseptic and used for cleaning wounds in piles, syphilis.

Drymaria cordata (L.) Willd. (Caryophyllaceae) RVY 13150 Plant juice antifebrile and laxative.

Elephantopus scaber L. (Compositae, Karipadam) RVY 13143

Plant extract remedy for elephantiasis, astringent, cardiac tonic, root extract given in dysuria, diarrhoea, stomach pain, dysentery, root in vomiting.

Eriolaena quinquelocularis Wight (Sterculiaceae, Bhagvat) RVY 13094

Roots are employed as poultice to heal wounds, antiseptic.

Eupatorium cannabinum L. (Compositae, Tongollati) RVY 13020

Plant diuretic, antiscorbutic, given in visceral obstructions, in leg swellings, intermittent fevers, for fomenting sores, in influenza.

Ficus bengalensis L. (Moraceae, Bargat or Bar) RVY 13056

Leaves antimicrobial used mouth ulcers, latex antiseptic applied on wounds, bark in dysentery and diabetes, buds infusion in diarrhoea, growing tips to stop vomiting, milky juice in external pains.

Ficus rumphii Blume Bijd. (Moraceae, Pakri) RVY 13057

Plant juice in antimicrobial, given with turmeric relieves cough and cold effects, bark in snake bite.

Ficus semicordata Buch.-Ham. (Moraceae, Khunia) RVY 13006

Fruits are given in aphatos complaints, bark water extract as bath to cure leprosy, root juice in liver complaints.

Flacourtia romantchi L' Herit. (Flacourtiaceae, Bilangra) RVY 13132

Fruits are given in enlargement of spleen and liver, useful in jaundice, bark diuretic, astringent.

Fragaria vesca L. (Rosaceae, Pahari rasbhari) RVY 13037

Fruits are aromatic, rich in protein and vit. C, astringent, diuretic, leaves infusion in diarrhoea and urinary diseases.

Geranium ocellatum Camb. (Geraniaceae) RVY 13004

Herb is astringent, employed in diarrhoea, haemorrhage, used in gargling in sore throat, applied on ulcers.

Grewia elastica Royle (Tiliaceae, Phalsa) RVY 13122

Root bark given in rheumatism, leaves antiseptic given pustular eruptions. *Haldina cordifolia* (Roxb.) Ridsdale (Rubiaceae, Haldu) RVY 13043

Bark antiseptic, leaf juice to kill worms in sores.

Helicterus isora L. (Sterculiaceae, Kapasi) RVY 13077

Dried fruits in intestinal disorders, colic pains, diarrhoea, roots given in amoebic dysentery, diabetes.

Hemidesmus indicus Br. (Asclepiadaceae, Anantamul) RVY 13064

Roots demulcent, tonic given in loss of appetite, in fevers, skin diseases, as blood purifier in leucorrhoea, syphilis.

Holarrhena antidysentrica Wall. (Apocynaceae, Kurchi or Kewar) RVY 13018

Stem and bark are astringent antidysenteric, anthelmintic, in colic pains, dyspepsia, piles, chest infection, skin and spleen complaints.

Indigofera tinctoria L. (Fabaceae, Nil or Me) RVY 13049

Plant extract in epilepsy, nervous disorders in bronchitis, as ointment for sores, old ulcers, antiseptic, roots in urinary troubles.

Kydia calycina Roxb. (Malvaceae, Baranga) RVY 13140

Leaf pastes in water for pains, skin diseases, leaves chewed to improve saliva.

Lagerstroemia reginae Roxb. (Lythraceae, Jarul) RVY 13063

Leaves purgative, diuretic, dried fruit extract for diabetes, bark stimulant used stomach pain and diarrhoea.

Lobelia heyneana Roem. (Lobeliaceae, Lobila) RVY 13131 Plant used in fevers, asthma, roots antirheumatic.

Madhuca indica J.F. Gmel (Sapotaceae, Mahua) RVY 13014

Flower tonic, appetizer, given in cough, pure ghee in piles, seed oil in skin diseases, constipation, headache.

Mollotus philippensis Muell. - Arg. (Euphorbiaceae, Kamala or Rohini) RVY 13022

Powder fruits are strong purgative, applied skin affected by parasites, scabies, ringworm and herpes, reduces fertility in females but given in low doses.

Micromeria capitellata Benth. (Labiatae, Lajauni) RVY 13103

Herb in source of peppermint used the preparation of digestive and other medicine, aromatic, stimulant, used in vomiting, headache, sprains, hot infusion in stomachache.

Millettia extensa (Benth.) Baker (Fabaceae, Maudh) RVY 13117

Roots insect repellent, root infusion applied skin diseases to keep off flies.

Moringa oleifera Lamk. (Moringaceae, Saunjana) RVY 13002

Flowers and roots are given in rheumatism, ascites, cardiac and circulatory stimulants, leaves applied on wounds, antiseptic, antipyretic, seed oil rheumatic pain.

Murraya koenigii Spreng. (Rutaceae, Karipatta) RVY 13088

Leaf pastes in digestive, tonic, stimulant, rich vit. A, bark given dysentery, diarrhoea, check vomiting, antiseptic.

Murraya paniculata (L.) Jack (Rutaceae, Kamini) RVY 13084

Leaves stimulant given in diarrhoea. powder dry leaves are antiseptic, leaves and root bark in rheumatism, cough, hysteria.

Naravelia zeylanica DC. (Ranunculaceae, Chagulbati) RVY 13062

Tender ones as tooth sticks in toothache, crushed fresh roots applied in headache.

Nyctanthes arbor-trisis L. (Oleaceae, Harsinghar) RVY 13024

Leaves antiseptic, given in fevers, rheumatism, leaf extract for sciatica, given to children to expel warm.

Osbeckia stellata Ker. - Gawl. (Melastomaceae, Tsulesi) RVY 13137 Root extract stomachic, accelerate digestion, dried leaves in toothache. *Physalia minima* L. (Solanaceae, Tulatipatti) RVY 13027

Fruits tonic, diuretic, purgative, useful in animal gonorrhoea, leaf juice with mustard oil in earache, fruits in ghee in spleen disorders.

Plectranthus mollis (Aiton.) Spr. (Labiatae, Lalagada) RVY 13171

Leaf and flowers essential oil is antiseptic and antibacterial, a cardiac depressant, respiratory stimulant, leaf past to stop bleeding and in fever, a good mosquito repellent.

Plumbago zeylanica L. (Plumbaginaceae, Chitramuli) RVY 131 1 5

Roots given in rheumatism, low doses in dyspepsia, pi les, diarrhoea, skin trou bles, leaves if eaten cause

abortion, root infusion in black water fever and influenza.

Polygala tatarinowii Regel. (Polygalaceae, Meradu) RVY 13085

Leaf infusion in asthma, chronic bronchitis, roots in fever and dizziness, antiseptic.

Pueraria tuberosa DC. (Fabaceae, Bilaikand) RVY 13170 Roots given in fevers, in joint swellings, as lactagogue.

Salix tetrasperma Roxb. (Salicaceae, Bilsa) RVY I 3041

Powdered leaves in rheumatism, epilepsy, swellings, piles, bladder stones, venereal diseases.

Santalum album L. (Santalaceae, Chandan) RVY 13114

Wood and oil diuretic, expectorant, household remedy in burns, given in fevers, in gonorrhoea. effective in skin ointments, antiseptic.

Schleichera oleosa (Lour.) Oxen. (Sapindaceae, Kusum) RVY 13045

Seed oil in skin diseases, massage in rheumatic pains, bark applied in itches, ulcers, macerated in water for malaria.

Semecarpus anacardium L. f. (Anacardiaceae, Bhelwa) RVY 13053

Fruit anthelmintic given ascites, tumours, warts, rheumatism, asthma, epilepsy, psoriasis, plant juice antibacterial.

Shorea robusta Gaertn. f. (Dipterocarpaceae, Sal or Sakhu) RVY 13054 Resin given in dysentery, in fumigation, given in indigestion in gonorrhoea. *Sida rhombifolia* L. (Malvaceae, Lalbarela) RVY 13164

Leaves in tuberculosis, rheumatism, roots in leucorrhoea.

Smilax ovalifolia Roxb. (Liliaceae, Romdatun) RVY 13167

Roots in venereal diseases, applied in rheumatic swellings, given dysentery, urinary complaints.

Sonchus oleraceus L. (Compositae, Dudhi) RVY 13019

Stem as sedative, tonic, its extract is used for making ointment for ulcer, wounds, gum used for ascites, hydrothorax.

Sonchus wightianus DC. (Compositae, Sahadevi) RVY 13011

Roots in cough, bronchitis, asthma, leaves applied on swelling, plant latex in eye troubles.

Sonerila tenera Royle (Melastomaceae, Huring) RVY 13176 Roots are used for treating throat diseases of cattles.

Spermadictyon suaveolens Roxb. (Rubiaceae, Budolhighasi) RVY 13061

Plant in antiseptic, used in wounds, bark powder in puerperal fever, root in diarrhoea.

Sterculia foetida L. (Sterculiaceae, Pinari) RVY 13153

Seeds bring abortion in ladies, bark aperients, diuretic, seed oil in rheumatism.

Sterculia villosa Roxb. (Sterculiaceae, Gulkandar) RVY 13173 Gum as antiseptic for animals wound.

Stereospermum colais (Dillw.) Mabblerley (Bignoniaceae, Parral) RVY 13179

Root extract in asthma, cough, excessive thirst, leaves in chronic dyspepsia, leaf juice in til oil in ear, teeth diseases and rheumatism.

Syzygium operculatum (Roxb.) Niedenzu (Myrtaceae, Rajjama n) RVY 13168

Fruits in rheumatism, leaves on swelling, root extract in joint pain.

Syzygium wallichii (W.) Walp. (Myrtaceae, Jamun) RVY 13112

Pulp stimulates, stomachic, good in colitis, seed powder antidiabetic, aphrodisiac.

Tectona grandis L. (Verbenaceae, Saguan) RVY 13038

Wood extract antiseptic, applied on swellings, wood ash in swollen eyelids, bark astringent.

Terminalia bellirica (Gaertn.) Roxb. (Combretaceae, Bahera) RVY 13017

Fruits bitter astringent, tonic, antipyretic, given in piles, dropsy, diarrhoea, headache, extract in leprosy, leaves in silk worm.

Terminalia chebula Retz obs. (Combretaceae, Harra) RVY 13029

Dried fruits applied on chronic ulcers, as gargle in stomatitis, in toothache, bleeding gums, bark diuretic, in asthma, in burns.

Tetrastigma lanceolarium (Roxb.) Plachon (Vitaceae, Bherseri) RVY 13097

Leaf poultice applied on boils, plant juice for cough.

Thalictrum foliolosum DC. (Ranunculaceae, Mamiri) RVY 13060

Roots extract as diuretic, antiperiodic, purgative, bitter tonic, powder in ophthalmia, in atonic dyspersia.

Thalictrum javanicum Blume Bijd (Ranunculaceae) RVY 13081

Dried rhizome as drug, a tonic, intermittent fevers, local people used for ophthalmia.

Thespesia lampas (Cav.) Dalz. (Malvaceae, Bankapas) RVY 13110 Fruits in gonorrhoea, syphilis.

Thysanolaena maxima (Roxb.) Kuntze (Gramineae, Phuljanta) RVY 13021 Root extract as mouthwash.

Toona ciliata R. (Meliaceae, Tun or Red cedar) RVY 13101

Bark astringent, tonic, chronic infantile dysentery, externally in ulcers.

Viola betonicifolia J. E. Smith (Violaceae) RVY 13109

Herb juice is antiseptic, applied on ulcers, syphilis, cancer, given mixed with gorshanda for cough and cold.

Woodfordia fruticosa (L.) Kurz (Lythraceae, Arishtas) RVY 13012

Dried flowers stimulant, bowel complaints, haemorrhages, seminal weakness, menorrhagia, cleaning ulcers, leaves antibiotic.

Zizyphus oenoplia Mill. (Rhamnaceae, Mahkua or Makoh) RVY 13080

Root bark in healing wounds, fruits in stomachache.

*Field diary number

OBSERVATION

The household remedies used by the tribal communities are presented in enumeration according to the plant species. The plant species have been arranged alphabetically according to their Botanical name, family, vernacular name/Local name, field diary number, plant parts used and mode of administration.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The authors are thankful to Dr. R. S. Singh, Principal and Prof. M. P. Singh, Department of Botany, Udai Pratap (Autonomous) College, Varanasi, for providing facilities and for his encouragement to carry out this investigation. Help extended by tribal informants is also acknowledged.

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